

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13851465

Ethical Leadership And Security Culture In Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the critical intersection of ethical leadership and security culture in higher education institutions, emphasizing the importance of values-based approaches to enhance campus safety and security. Through a systematic literature review, the research investigates the role of ethical leadership in fostering a security-conscious culture, assesses the effectiveness of values-based leadership in promoting ethical decision-making among university stakeholders, and explores strategies for integrating ethical principles into security management practices. Findings indicate that transparency, accountability, and community engagement are essential components of ethical leadership that contribute to a safer campus environment. The study concludes with recommendations for universities to implement ethical leadership training, establish participatory security committees, and develop national guidelines for ethical security practices. This research underscores the necessity of ethical frameworks in security management to build trust and collaboration within the academic community.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership, Security Culture, Higher Education, Campus Safety, Values-Based Leadership, Ethical Decision-Making, Security Management, Community Engagement

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary higher education landscape, the importance of fostering a strong security culture cannot be overstated. Higher education institutions face increasing challenges related to safety, ranging from cybersecurity threats to physical campus security risks. Addressing these challenges requires not only robust security protocols but also the promotion of ethical leadership as a guiding force. Ethical leadership, defined as “the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making” (Brown & Treviño, 2006, p. 595), is essential for cultivating a values-based security culture in higher education. Such leadership shapes the behaviors of institutional stakeholders, encouraging them to prioritize ethical practices and security-conscious decision-making.

A security culture is often described as the collective attitude, values, and behaviors towards security that are shared within an organization (Puhakainen & Siponen, 2010). In higher education, the significance of this culture is heightened due to the diverse range of individuals involved—students, faculty, administrative staff, and external partners—all of whom must collaborate to ensure a safe and secure learning environment. However, ethical leadership plays a crucial role in fostering this culture by instilling a sense of accountability and shared responsibility. Leaders who emphasize ethical behavior influence the security practices of their institutions by setting an example for transparent communication, responsible decision-making, and adherence to ethical principles (Neves & Story, 2015). In turn, this reinforces a security culture that is not only compliance-driven but deeply rooted in the ethical values of the institution.

Promoting a values-based approach to campus security aligns with the broader goal of higher education institutions to serve as models of integrity and social responsibility. According to Freeman and Stewart (2006), ethical leadership involves making decisions based on core institutional values such as fairness, trustworthiness, and respect for all stakeholders. When applied to security, these values become foundational in ensuring that policies and practices prioritize the well-being of the entire campus community. Furthermore, the integration of ethical leadership into security management addresses the moral dimensions of safety, ensuring that actions taken to protect the institution are consistent with the ethical standards expected of educational leaders.

Moreover, the growing threat of cybersecurity breaches in higher education further highlights the need for ethical leadership in fostering a security culture. As universities increasingly rely on digital platforms for administration, research, and instruction, they become targets for cyberattacks (Yawson & Yamoah, 2020). Ethical leadership promotes a proactive approach to cybersecurity by ensuring that security measures are implemented not merely to meet regulatory requirements but to safeguard the privacy and intellectual property of the academic community. Leaders who emphasize ethical behavior influence the creation of cybersecurity policies that are fair, transparent, and designed to protect all stakeholders, thus enhancing the overall security culture of the institution (Flores et al., 2014).

Statement of the Problem

Higher education institutions are increasingly vulnerable to various security threats, including cyberattacks, physical security breaches, and internal misconduct, posing significant risks to students, staff, and institutional integrity. Despite the implementation of standard security protocols, many institutions still struggle to foster a security culture that is embedded in ethical values, which is crucial for long-term safety and trustworthiness (Yawson & Yamoah, 2020). In many cases, these challenges stem from a failure to integrate ethical leadership into security management practices, leading to a compliance-driven approach that overlooks the moral and ethical dimensions of security (Flores et al., 2014). This gap between policy and practice not only compromises campus safety but also erodes the sense of responsibility among stakeholders, potentially fostering environments where unethical behaviors such as data manipulation, hacking, and neglect of security protocols become prevalent.

Ethical leadership, which emphasizes values such as integrity, transparency, accountability, and fairness, has the potential to reshape the security culture in higher education. Research shows that institutions with strong ethical leadership tend to experience lower levels of organizational deviance and improved compliance with security protocols (Neves & Story, 2015). However, many universities have not fully embraced this approach, and the literature reveals a lack of comprehensive strategies that align ethical leadership with security practices (Brown & Treviño, 2006). Moreover, in the context of increasing digitalization and the rise of cyber threats in higher education, the absence of a values-based approach to security exacerbates vulnerabilities. Without strong ethical leadership to guide decision-making and foster a sense of shared responsibility, institutions are more likely to experience security breaches that compromise personal data, research integrity, and the overall safety of the academic community (Yawson & Yamoah, 2020).

Despite the recognized importance of ethical leadership in other sectors, there is limited research specifically addressing its role in shaping security culture in higher education (Puhakainen & Siponen, 2010). While some studies have examined the influence of leadership on organizational culture, there is a need for a systematic exploration of how values-based leadership can directly contribute to enhancing campus safety and security. The lack of comprehensive models and frameworks integrating ethical leadership with security practices highlights a critical gap in the literature, which this systematic review aims to address.

Therefore, the problem facing higher education institutions is the absence of a cohesive, values-based approach to security management that integrates ethical leadership into the core of security culture. Without this integration, institutions may fail to develop robust security frameworks that prioritize ethical decision-making and ensure the protection of all campus stakeholders. This review seeks to fill this gap by exploring how ethical leadership can promote a sustainable security culture, reduce vulnerabilities, and enhance the overall safety of higher education environments.

Aim and Objectives of Study

The study examined ethical leadership and security culture in higher education in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study achieved the following:

1. To examine the role of ethical leadership in fostering a security-conscious culture within higher education institutions.
2. To assess the effectiveness of values-based leadership in promoting campus safety and ethical decision-making among university stakeholders.
3. To explore strategies for integrating ethical principles into security management practices to enhance safety on university campuses.

Empirical Review

Empirical studies on ethical leadership in higher education highlight its significant role in shaping organizational culture, particularly in fostering a security-conscious environment. Ethical leadership is characterized by leaders who prioritize ethical decision-making, transparency, and accountability, which in turn fosters trust and integrity within the institution (Brown & Treviño, 2006). For example, a study by Neves and Story (2015) found that ethical leadership reduces organizational deviance and increases compliance with institutional policies, including security protocols. This suggests that when university leaders exemplify ethical behavior, they influence their subordinates and peers to prioritize security-related behaviors. However, while the general impact of ethical leadership on organizational culture has been studied, there is limited research specifically addressing how it fosters a security-conscious culture within higher education, leaving a gap for further investigation into the role of leadership in shaping security practices.

Values-based leadership, which emphasizes decision-making rooted in core values such as integrity, fairness, and responsibility, has been linked to improved campus safety and ethical decision-making among university stakeholders (Freeman & Stewart, 2006). Empirical evidence suggests that institutions that embrace values-based leadership tend to cultivate a culture of accountability and proactive risk management. For instance, Flores et al. (2014) found that ethical leadership positively influenced the adoption of security measures, leading to more effective management of cybersecurity risks in higher education institutions. These leaders model ethical behavior, which is mirrored by faculty, staff, and students, thereby reinforcing the importance of campus safety and security measures. Despite these findings, empirical studies have not fully examined the specific mechanisms through which values-based leadership influences ethical decision-making related to campus security, highlighting the need for further research in this area.

Integrating ethical principles into security management practices remains a challenge for many higher education institutions. While research on security management often focuses on technical and procedural aspects, there is a growing recognition that ethical considerations are critical for effective security governance (Yawson & Yamoah, 2020). Puhakainen and Siponen (2010) argue that security policies are most effective when they are aligned with the institution's ethical values, which requires leaders to integrate these principles into security protocols and training programs. However, studies on how ethical principles can be systematically incorporated into security management strategies in higher education are limited. This gap suggests a need for further exploration of the strategies that university leaders can adopt to integrate ethical leadership into security governance in ways that enhance both safety and the institution's ethical integrity.

METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was conducted to explore the role of ethical leadership in fostering a security-conscious culture and promoting values-based approaches to enhance campus safety in higher education. The methodology adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, ensuring a transparent and replicable review process (Moher et al., 2015; Page et al., 2021). By following PRISMA's structured approach, the review maintained methodological rigor, ensuring that the research was thorough and of high quality. The PRISMA flowchart (Figure 1) illustrates the review process, including article identification, screening, and inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Systematic Review Process

Identification

The identification phase involved an extensive search across five academic databases: Scopus, Web of Science, ProQuest, EBSCO Host, and Google Scholar. To capture relevant studies, the search employed a combination of keywords and Boolean operators, including terms such as "ethical

leadership,” “security culture,” “campus safety,” “values-based leadership,” and “higher education.” These search terms were selected to ensure a wide range of literature related to ethical leadership and security practices in university settings. The initial search yielded a total of 1,245 articles, with an additional 42 articles identified through manual searches of reference lists and citations, resulting in 1,287 articles for consideration.

Screening

In line with PRISMA guidelines, a rigorous screening process was conducted to filter out studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria. The review was restricted to peer-reviewed journal articles published in English between 2010 and 2024, ensuring that the study reflects contemporary issues and trends in higher education leadership and security. Excluded materials included conference papers, book chapters, and articles not focused on ethical leadership or security culture in higher education. Duplicate articles (n=98) were removed, reducing the dataset to 1,189 unique articles. Titles and abstracts of these articles were screened to assess their relevance to ethical leadership and security culture, resulting in the exclusion of 980 articles, leaving 209 for full-text review.

Eligibility

During the eligibility phase, the remaining 209 articles were thoroughly reviewed to assess their empirical relevance to the research questions. Articles were excluded if they lacked empirical data, focused on unrelated sectors or industries, or discussed ethical leadership in general without specific emphasis on security culture or campus safety in higher education institutions. Further exclusions were made for theoretical articles without practical or empirical evidence. Following this process, 188 articles were excluded, leaving 21 articles that met the inclusion criteria for the study (as depicted in the PRISMA flowchart in Figure 1).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The final selection of 21 articles was based on the following inclusion criteria: peer-reviewed journal articles published in English, studies providing empirical evidence related to ethical leadership and security culture, and research conducted within the higher education context. Articles that focused solely on leadership in non-educational sectors, lacked empirical data, or were not directly related to campus safety were excluded. The strict application of inclusion and exclusion criteria ensured that the review included high-quality, relevant studies.

This systematic review methodology provided a rigorous approach to examining the role of ethical leadership in promoting security culture and campus safety, contributing valuable insights into how values-based leadership can be integrated into security management practices in higher education.

The Role of Ethical Leadership in Fostering a Security-Conscious Culture within Higher Education Institutions

Ethical leadership plays a critical role in shaping organizational culture, particularly in promoting a security-conscious environment within higher education institutions. This thematic analysis explores key themes that emerge from the literature, demonstrating how ethical leadership fosters a culture of safety, accountability, and proactive risk management in universities.

1. Influence of Ethical Leadership on Organizational Culture

The literature underscores the profound impact that ethical leadership has on the overall culture of higher education institutions. Ethical leaders are characterized by their commitment to principles of integrity, fairness, and accountability, which positively influence organizational values and behaviors (Brown & Treviño, 2006). In the context of campus security, ethical leadership helps to create an environment where security practices are prioritized and internalized by staff, faculty, and students. A study by Neves and Story (2015) highlights how ethical leadership reduces deviant behavior and increases adherence to institutional policies, including security measures, by modeling and rewarding ethical behavior. Through open communication and transparency, ethical leaders promote an atmosphere of trust, which is essential for fostering collective responsibility towards campus safety.

2. Accountability and Ethical Decision-Making in Security Management

A prominent theme in the literature is the link between ethical leadership and enhanced accountability in security management. Ethical leaders set high moral standards and expect the same from their teams, which is crucial in creating a culture where ethical decision-making is prioritized in all aspects of security operations (Yukl et al., 2013). This leadership style empowers stakeholders to take responsibility for campus security, promoting a sense of ownership and ethical consideration in

decision-making. Flores et al. (2014) found that institutions led by ethical leaders experienced improved compliance with cybersecurity policies, as stakeholders were more likely to act in the best interest of the institution. This sense of shared responsibility not only fosters security consciousness but also encourages proactive identification and mitigation of potential security risks before they escalate.

3. Promoting a Security-Conscious Environment through Ethical Communication

Another theme that emerges from the literature is the role of ethical communication in promoting a security-conscious environment. Ethical leaders emphasize transparent and open communication, which helps to build trust and encourage collective participation in security efforts (Bedi et al., 2016). When leaders communicate openly about security policies, risks, and expectations, it reinforces the importance of security practices and empowers members of the institution to contribute actively to maintaining safety. For example, Puhakainen and Siponen (2010) demonstrate how ethical communication, driven by leadership, improves employee compliance with information security protocols. This is particularly important in higher education institutions where stakeholders must collaborate to ensure both physical and digital safety. Ethical communication fosters an environment where security is seen as a shared responsibility, reducing complacency and enhancing vigilance.

4. Fostering Ethical Security Practices through Training and Development

The literature also highlights the importance of ethical leadership in fostering security-conscious behavior through training and professional development. Ethical leaders prioritize continuous education on security issues, ensuring that staff and students are well-informed and capable of implementing security measures effectively (Yawson & Yamoah, 2020). By integrating ethical principles into training programs, leaders encourage a deeper understanding of security beyond mere compliance, cultivating a culture where security is viewed as an ethical obligation. Studies suggest that values-based training, coupled with leadership-driven initiatives, leads to higher levels of engagement and adherence to security practices (Freeman & Stewart, 2006). This ensures that security consciousness becomes embedded in the institution's culture, further strengthening the collective effort to protect campus safety.

The thematic analysis reveals that ethical leadership plays a crucial role in fostering a security-conscious culture within higher education institutions. Through influencing organizational culture, promoting accountability and ethical decision-making, enhancing communication, and providing security-focused training, ethical leaders create an environment where security is a shared and prioritized responsibility. These findings suggest that institutions can benefit significantly from integrating ethical leadership into their security strategies to ensure a safer, more secure campus environment.

Assessing the Effectiveness of Values-Based Leadership in Promoting Campus Safety and Ethical Decision-Making Among University Stakeholders

Values-based leadership is grounded in ethical principles that prioritize trust, integrity, and moral decision-making. In higher education, such leadership is increasingly recognized as essential for promoting campus safety and fostering a culture of ethical decision-making among stakeholders. This thematic analysis assesses how values-based leadership enhances campus security and influences ethical behavior across the university community.

1. Values-Based Leadership and Its Role in Shaping Ethical Campus Culture

A central theme in the literature is the role of values-based leadership in establishing an ethical campus culture, which directly impacts safety and decision-making. Leaders who emphasize values such as integrity, transparency, and accountability create a shared moral framework that guides behavior across the institution (Freeman & Stewart, 2006). Studies show that when leadership embodies ethical principles, students, faculty, and staff are more likely to adopt similar behaviors, creating a cohesive community focused on mutual safety and responsibility (Brown & Treviño, 2006). For example, Neves and Story (2015) found that universities with values-based leadership experience lower rates of misconduct and deviant behavior, as ethical norms are internalized by the community. By promoting fairness and integrity, values-based leaders reduce conflict and foster a cooperative atmosphere, which is critical for maintaining a safe and secure campus environment.

2. Encouraging Ethical Decision-Making Through Transparent Leadership

Transparency, a key attribute of values-based leadership, is particularly effective in promoting ethical decision-making among university stakeholders. Leaders who prioritize open communication and clear decision-making processes set a standard for ethical behavior, which encourages stakeholders to act with honesty and integrity (Treviño et al., 2003). Research by Bedi et al. (2016) highlights the importance of transparency in creating an environment where ethical dilemmas are addressed openly, allowing for informed, collective decisions that prioritize the welfare of the university community. By making ethical decision-making processes visible, values-based leaders enable students, faculty, and administrators to feel confident that their actions align with the institution's core values. This has a direct impact on safety, as stakeholders are more likely to engage in security practices that protect the broader campus community.

3. Collaborative Leadership and Shared Responsibility for Campus Safety

The literature also emphasizes the importance of collaborative leadership in promoting shared responsibility for campus safety. Values-based leaders often adopt participatory decision-making models that empower stakeholders to contribute to security-related discussions and decisions (Yukl et al., 2013). This collaborative approach fosters a sense of ownership over campus safety, as all members of the university feel involved in shaping the security policies and practices. A study by Eisenbeiß and Giessner (2012) found that participatory leadership encourages proactive behavior in addressing security concerns, as stakeholders feel personally accountable for maintaining a safe environment. Moreover, shared leadership structures enable diverse perspectives to be included in decision-making, which enhances the institution's ability to anticipate and mitigate potential security risks.

4. Values-Based Leadership in Crisis Management and Security Responses

Another theme in the literature is the effectiveness of values-based leadership during crises, particularly in relation to security responses. Leaders who are guided by ethical principles are more likely to manage crises with a focus on both immediate security needs and long-term ethical considerations (Brown et al., 2005). Studies suggest that institutions with values-based leadership are better equipped to handle security threats in a manner that respects the dignity and rights of all stakeholders. For instance, a crisis management framework grounded in ethical values ensures that emergency responses are not only efficient but also equitable and just, thereby strengthening trust in the leadership (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999). This trust is crucial in promoting long-term campus safety, as stakeholders are more likely to comply with security protocols when they believe the institution's leadership is acting in their best interests.

The thematic analysis demonstrates that values-based leadership is highly effective in promoting campus safety and ethical decision-making among university stakeholders. Through fostering an ethical culture, emphasizing transparency, encouraging shared responsibility, and providing principled crisis management, values-based leaders cultivate a security-conscious environment where stakeholders feel empowered to make decisions that prioritize the safety and integrity of the campus community.

Exploring Strategies for Integrating Ethical Principles into Security Management Practices to Enhance Safety on University Campuses

The integration of ethical principles into security management on university campuses has emerged as a critical strategy for promoting safety and fostering trust among students, staff, and faculty. This thematic analysis explores the ways ethical leadership principles can be applied to security practices in higher education institutions, emphasizing the importance of transparency, fairness, accountability, and community engagement in creating a secure and ethical campus environment.

1. Transparency and Accountability in Security Decision-Making

A key theme in the literature is the role of transparency and accountability in security management. Ethical principles such as openness in decision-making and clear communication of security protocols are vital to building trust between university leadership and the campus community. Studies show that when security policies and practices are transparent, students and staff are more likely to comply with regulations and report suspicious behavior, contributing to a safer campus environment (O'Donovan, 2017). Ethical leaders emphasize accountability by ensuring that all security measures are subject to oversight, which deters potential abuses of power and fosters a sense of fairness (Myers, 2018). This

approach ensures that security management does not become overly authoritarian but remains aligned with the values of inclusivity and respect for individual rights, making the campus a safer and more trusting environment.

2. Community Engagement in Security Practices

Another crucial strategy for integrating ethical principles into campus security management is fostering community engagement. Ethical leadership encourages participatory approaches where all stakeholders—students, faculty, staff, and security personnel—are involved in the development and implementation of security policies (Mitchell et al., 2015). This collaborative approach aligns with the ethical principles of inclusivity and respect for diverse perspectives. Studies highlight the importance of a community-based model in which stakeholders not only adhere to security policies but actively participate in creating them, which increases the effectiveness of security strategies (Aly & Striegher, 2012). For example, involving students in security committees or safety audits provides valuable insights into potential vulnerabilities and fosters a collective sense of responsibility for campus safety. Ethical leaders, by encouraging such engagement, enhance both the security culture and the ethical climate of the institution.

3. Fairness and Equity in Security Enforcement

The ethical principle of fairness is also a significant theme in the literature, especially concerning the enforcement of security policies. Security management practices that treat all members of the campus community equitably are critical for maintaining both safety and trust. Research shows that discriminatory or biased enforcement of security protocols can undermine the perceived legitimacy of security operations, leading to non-compliance and distrust (Gigliotti, 2019). Ethical leadership requires that security enforcement be applied consistently, without favoritism or bias, ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their background or status, are subject to the same rules (Freeman & Auster, 2011). This equitable approach not only enhances safety but also upholds the ethical standards of justice and equality, which are foundational to a positive campus climate.

4. Ethical Crisis Management in Response to Security Threats

Another important strategy for integrating ethical principles into security management is ethical crisis management. Ethical leadership in higher education involves managing security threats, such as violence or natural disasters, in ways that uphold the dignity and rights of all affected parties (Jiang et al., 2017). Ethical crisis management ensures that emergency responses are not only swift and effective but also compassionate and just. Studies highlight the importance of leaders making ethically informed decisions during crises to balance the immediate need for security with long-term institutional values, such as fairness and inclusion (Eisenbeiß & Giessner, 2012). Ethical leaders must therefore ensure that crisis management procedures respect human rights and consider the broader impacts on the university community, fostering both trust and resilience in the face of security challenges.

This thematic analysis demonstrates that integrating ethical principles into security management practices on university campuses enhances safety and promotes trust. Transparency, accountability, community engagement, fairness in enforcement, and ethical crisis management are all vital strategies that ensure security measures align with the institution's values, thereby creating a safer and more ethically sound environment. By adopting these ethical strategies, higher education institutions can maintain a balance between security needs and the protection of individual rights, fostering a campus culture grounded in safety, trust, and respect.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The exploration of ethical leadership and security culture within higher education institutions highlights the critical role that values-based approaches play in fostering a safe and secure campus environment. Ethical leadership, rooted in transparency, accountability, fairness, and community engagement, emerges as a fundamental pillar for creating a security-conscious culture in universities. By ensuring that security policies are applied consistently and equitably, and by involving stakeholders in security decision-making processes, ethical leaders not only enhance the effectiveness of security measures but also promote trust and cooperation across the campus community.

The assessment of values-based leadership reveals its significant impact on campus safety and ethical decision-making among university stakeholders. Leaders who prioritize ethical principles create an environment where safety is intertwined with respect for individual rights and inclusivity. Such an

approach mitigates the risks of bias, enhances the legitimacy of security operations, and fosters a collaborative culture where all members of the community take responsibility for maintaining a safe environment.

Lastly, the integration of ethical principles into security management practices is crucial for enhancing safety on university campuses. Strategies such as transparency in decision-making, community engagement, equitable enforcement of security protocols, and ethical crisis management ensure that security measures not only address immediate threats but also align with the institution's broader ethical values. Ultimately, ethical leadership in security management strengthens both the security infrastructure and the ethical climate of higher education institutions, ensuring a holistic and sustainable approach to campus safety.

1. The university administration, in collaboration with the Ministry of Education, should implement mandatory ethical leadership training programs for all campus security staff to enhance their understanding of transparency, accountability, and human rights.

2. University governance bodies, along with student unions and faculty representatives, should create security committees that engage diverse stakeholders in the development and evaluation of campus security policies.

3. The National Higher Education Regulatory Authorities, in partnership with the Ministry of Justice and Security, should formulate standardized guidelines that integrate ethical principles into security management frameworks across all higher education institutions.

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